

ONE OF THE MOST ACCURATE EXPERIMENTS IN THE WORLD REFUSES THE CONCLUSIONS OF THE SPECIAL THEORY OF RELATIVITY

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Abstract. From 1999 to 2014 In Bottler, Colorado, scientists at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) conducted what appears to be one of the most precise experiments in the history of physics, during which readings of some of the the most accurate clocks in the world, located in different parts of the globe at different latitudes. The experiment showed that, regardless of the latitude of the location of the 12 clocks that were observed, absolutely all clocks tick exactly the same way. This experiment calls into question the reliability of the conclusions of the special theory of relativity (STR), according to which clocks located at different latitudes, due to different linear speeds of movement in a circle due to rotation around the earth's axis, should move at different speeds. Clocks located closer to the equator, according to SRT, should run slower and, over time, lag behind clocks located closer to the poles.

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Introduction

In 2022, in St. Petersburg, using radar, 100 scientists and engineers (including 8 doctors, 24 candidates of science and 20 graduate students) conducted an experiment to monitor the observed progress of clocks located on aircraft directly during flight. With the highest confidence probability equal to 0.9999999999744, the experiment showed that the theoretical conclusion of SRT about the slowdown of the observed rate of a moving clock if it moves towards the observer is unreliable [1-3]. This experiment became known to the public due to the fact that the scientific article in which its results were published received the title “Property of the Nation” according to the “international register of achievements and records”! The authors of the article were awarded the corresponding certificate “The largest scientific team of authors refuting the special theory of relativity.” This event received coverage in a number of media, a far from complete list of which is presented in [4-8].

However, the results of one experiment are apparently not enough to unequivocally speak about the refutation of SRT. Other experiments are needed to refute some other provisions of STR.

This work describes one of these most high-precision experiments in the entire history of physics.

The relevance of the work is due to the fact that the effects predicted by STR must be taken into account when developing navigation and surveillance systems in aviation and

astronautics to improve the accuracy of these systems [9-11]. Using an erroneous theory can lead to errors in the operation of these systems.

Experiment by scientists at the National Institute of Standards and Technology NIST

The experiment in question was conducted from November 1999 to October 2014. at the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) in Boulder, Colorado. During this experiment, scientists observed the progress of frequency standards used by leading metrologists at NIST , as well as in laboratories in the USA, France, Germany, Italy and the UK [12-14].

Observations of the 12 most accurate clocks in the world were carried out over more than 14 years. These clocks are located motionless at points at different latitudes of the globe, which move around the earth's axis with different linear speeds equal to

$$v = \cos \varphi R_3 \Omega,$$

where φ is the latitude of the clock location point;

R_3 – radius of the globe;

Ω – angular velocity of the Earth's rotation, rad/s.

During the experiment, it turned out that all the observed clocks ran exactly the same for 14 years, despite their different linear speeds around the Earth.

Controversy with STO

According to the special theory of relativity (STR), moving clocks run slower than stationary ones, and that is why various paradoxes of the theory of relativity arise, including the twin paradox.

When a clock moves in a circle around the earth's axis, clocks located closer to the equator move at a higher linear speed than clocks located closer to the poles (Fig. 1). Clocks located at the equator have the highest linear speed.

The radius of the Earth at the equator is 6378 km, so clocks located at the equator, due to the rotation of the Earth, rush at a speed exceeding the speed of sound, namely 464 m/sec (more than 1600 km/h). The speed of most civil aviation aircraft does not exceed a thousand km/h. A clock located at a pole does not have linear speed.

Therefore, according to SRT, clocks located closer to the equator, due to the higher speed of movement, should run slower than clocks located closer to the pole. Clock *A* , which is located on the equator, should run slower than clock *B* at mid-latitudes , and clocks *B* must go slower than clock *C* at the North Pole (Fig. 1).

In his work “On the Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies,” Einstein wrote, “If there are two synchronously running clocks at point *A* and we move one of them along a closed curve at a constant speed until they return to *A* (which will require, say, t sec), then this clock, upon arrival at *A*, will lag behind the clock that remained motionless by $(1/2) t (v / c) ^ 2$. From this we can conclude that a clock with a balancer, located on the earth's equator, should go somewhat slower than exactly the same clock placed at the pole, but otherwise placed in the same conditions” [15].

Fig. 1. SRT predicts: clock A runs slower than clock B, and clock B go slower than clock C due to the different speed of clock movement in a circle around the earth's axis.

NIST experiment refutes SRT: all clocks run **the same**

Einstein gives a formula that allows you to calculate the amount of lag of a clock τ moving at a speed v compared to a stationary clock:

$$\tau = \frac{t}{2} \left(\frac{v}{c} \right)^2,$$

where t is the time period for observing the clock (a year, for example), expressed in seconds;
 c is the speed of light.

Calculations show that, according to SRT, an atomic clock located at the equator, moving at a speed of 464 m/sec, in one year should lag behind the same stationary clock located at the pole by 37.74 microseconds. Over 14 years, the clock at the equator should lag behind the clock at the pole by 0.53 milliseconds.

A clock located in Italy should have fallen behind a clock located in Germany by about 0.1 milliseconds (100 microseconds) over 14 years.

This is a very large value by modern standards, since the error of modern frequency standards is less than one second over tens of millions of years, over 14 years - less than a microsecond (a hundred times less than what is required to detect clock lag).

Modern atomic clocks are more than accurate enough to detect Einstein's prediction of the slowing down of equatorial clocks relative to those at the poles.

However, during the experiment, NIST scientists found that all the observed clocks ran exactly the same for 14 years, despite their different linear speeds around the Earth's axis due to the Earth's rotation.

NIST Scientists' Findings

The scientists who conducted the experiment conclude that the laws of physics remain unchanged over time (at least they remained unchanged during the 14-year experiment).

The experimental results refute SRT

But the experimenters did not pay attention to the fact that their experiment, in fact, refutes the SRT, according to which clocks located at different latitudes should run at different speeds. The results of the experiment proved with the highest degree of accuracy the fact that the movement of a clock does not affect its progress, and that a moving clock runs exactly the same as a stationary clock.

NIST scientists, essentially refutes the special theory of relativity, according to which clocks moving at a faster speed should lag behind clocks moving at a slower speed.

Due to the fact that the effects predicted by STR need to be taken into account in navigation and surveillance systems in the aviation and space industries in order to increase the accuracy of these systems, it is necessary to develop an alternative theory to STR that does not contradict the results of the experiment of NIST scientists. Such a theory, in our opinion, is the Theory of Aberration - the first alternative theory to SRT, which has been confirmed experimentally [9-11]. A popular scientific presentation of the Theory of Aberration is presented in [16, 17].

Conclusion

Thus, as a result of an experiment by 100 scientists and engineers conducted in St. Petersburg in 2022 with a confidence probability of 0.9999999999744, it was established that the SRT conclusion about the slowdown of the observed clock readings in the case of movement towards the observer is erroneous.

conducted by NIST scientists revealed that all clocks on Earth, despite the fact that they are located at different latitudes and therefore move at different linear speeds around the Earth's axis due to the Earth's rotation, are exactly the same. According to SRT, clocks located closer to the equator should run slower than clocks located closer to the poles.

A 14-year experiment refutes SRT with the highest accuracy.

To improve the accuracy of navigation and surveillance systems in aviation and astronautics, an alternative theory to STR is required that does not contradict experiments. Such a theory is the Theory of Aberration [9-11, 16-17].

Please send your comments and suggestions regarding this work by email. mail: al.plyasovskih@yandex.ru

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